

Derivatives of Titanium with Compounds having Bidentate Ligands. Part VII. Derivatives with 2-Hydroxyethylamine

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The products $Ti(OR)_3(O.C_2H_4.NH_2)$, $Ti(OR)_2(O.C_2H_4.NH_2)_2$, $Ti(OR)(O.C_2H_4.NH_2)_3$, $Ti(O.C_2H_4.NH_2)_4$, and $Ti(O.C_2H_4.NH_2)_4.HO.C_2H_4.NH_2$ have been obtained as white solids in quantitative yield by the reaction between titanium alkoxides and 2-hydroxyethylamine (molar ratio 1:1 to 1: > 5). The first two are soluble in benzene and are dimeric in nature. Titanium penta-2-hydroxyethylamine derivative on heating under reduced pressure loses a molecule of the amine and titanium tetra-2-hydroxyethylamine is obtained.

There has been considerable interest in the organic derivatives of titanium in recent years, both from academic as well as technical points of view. Alkoxides of titanium have recently received much attention, but except for a reference to the possible use of titanium butoxide-ethanolamine product with methyl polysiloxane for insulation purposes¹, no work seems to have been done on these compounds. A detailed study of the reactions between various alk oxides of titanium and 2-hydroxyethylamine has been carried out and the reactions have been found very similar to the alcohol-interchange reactions studied previously in the case of titanium alkoxides and higher alcohols². The alkoxides used were eth oxide, isopropoxide, and butoxide³.

The reactions of titanium alkoxides with 2-hydroxyethylamine (molar ratio of 1:1 to 1:>5) can be quantitatively represented by the equations:

These compounds are crystalline solids. Trialkoxy-mono-2-hydroxyethylamine and dialkoxo-bis-2-hydroxyethylamine derivatives are soluble in benzene whereas other compounds are almost insoluble. The molecular weights of the compounds (I) and (II)

1. Peyrot and Dumulin, German Patent, 959329/1957; *Chem. Abs.*, 1963, 54, 16587.

2. Bradley *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4204, 5020; 1953, 2025.

been determined ebullioscopically in benzene and have been found to be dimer. These could be represented by the following plausible formulations:

(Ia)

(Ib)

(II)

Titanium penta-2-hydroxyethylamine, when heated under reduced pressure, lost one mole of the amine and changed to tetra-2-hydroxyethylamine compound.

EXPERIMENTAL

All-glass apparatus with interchangeable joints was used to exclude moisture from the apparatus as well as the reactants³. Molecular weights were determined on a semimicro ebulliometer (Gallankamp)³.

Titanium alkoxides (ethoxide, isopropoxide, and butoxide⁴) were distilled and analysed before use. 2-Hydroxyethylamine was distilled under reduced pressure at 80°/0.5 mm. Benzene was dried over sodium wire and finally fractionated azeotropically with ethanol.

Titanium was estimated as dioxide; ethanol and isopropanol in the azeotrope were estimated iodimetrically after the oxidation by normal potassium dichromate solution in 12% H₂SO₄. Nitrogen was estimated by the Kjeldahl method.

Reactions between Titanium Alkoxides and 2-Hydroxyethylamine in Benzene

(i) *In the Molar Ratio of 1:1.*—To titanium alkoxide, dissolved in excess benzene, was added one mole of 2-hydroxyethylamine. On shaking very little heat was evolved. The solution remained colorless and clear. The mixture was refluxed for about one hour (bath temperature 120°) and then slowly the azeotrope was taken till the temperature reached 80°. On cooling and keeping for some time, a clear solution was obtained. In case of ethoxide and isopropoxide, some white crystals were also obtained. The crystals were separated from the supernatant liquid and dried under reduced pressure. From the supernatant liquid the volatile matter was removed under reduced pressure and a white crystalline powder was obtained. In case of butoxide², a colorless viscous liquid was formed. The analysis of titanium in both precipitate and filtrate was found to be the same (Table I; No. 1, 2, 3).

(ii) *In the Molar Ratio of 1:2.*—To titanium alkoxide in excess of benzene were added 2 moles of 2-hydroxyethylamine. Heat was evolved on shaking, but no colour change took place. After refluxing for 2 hours (bath temperature 140°) the azeotrope was taken and the mixture was cooled. On cooling a white crystalline solid separated. The supernatant liquid was taken in another flask and the solid was dried under reduced pressure at 40–50°. The supernatant liquid also contained a small amount of the compound. Both the solids gave similar results (Table I; No. 4, 5, 6).

(iii) *In the Molar Ratio of 1:3.*—To titanium alkoxide in excess of benzene were added 3 moles of 2-hydroxyethylamine. Heat was produced without any colour change. The mixture was refluxed for 2 hours (145° bath temperature) and then the azeotrope was taken till the temperature reached 80°. On removing the bath, a white solid separated and the benzene remained slightly pink while hot, but on cooling it became colorless. The supernatant liquid was decanted and the solid was dried under reduced pressure at 40° (Table II; No. 1, 2, 3).

(iv) *In the Molar Ratio of 1:4.*—To titanium alkoxide in benzene was added 2-hydroxyethylamine (1:4). On shaking heat was produced. The mixture became slightly turbid, but a clear solution was obtained on heating. The mixture was refluxed for 1 hour (bath temperature 120°) and then the azeotrope was taken till the temperature reached 80°. On removing the bath, a light pink-coloured solution was obtained containing at the bottom a viscous liquid of light pink in colour. On cooling, the supernatant liquid became colorless and the viscous liquid solidified to a white product. The supernatant liquid was decanted and the solid was dried under reduced pressure at 60° (Table II; No. 4, 5).

To a portion of the compound (1.11 g.) was added benzene (35.0 g.). The mixture was shaken and then refluxed for about half hour at a bath of 130° and kept for 1 hour to settle the undissolved compound. The benzene was decanted in another flask and the solid was dried (1.05 g.) under reduced pressure. [Found: Ti, 16.89. $\text{Ti}(\text{O}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)_4$ requires Ti, 16.63%].

(v) *In the Molar Ratio of 1:5 or excess.*—(a) To titanium alkoxide in benzene was added 2-hydroxyethylamine (1:5). Heat was produced on shaking the reaction mixture. The azeotrope was taken after refluxing the mixture for 2 hours. On removing the bath, a light pink-coloured solution was obtained. At the bottom there was a light pink viscous mass. On cooling, the colour disappeared and the supernatant liquid was taken in

TABLE I

Sl. No.	Reactants.	Product, state, and yield.	%Titanium.		%Nitrogen.		Alcohol in azeotrope.		Distillation.
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	
1.	Ti(OEt) ₄ (1.27g.)	Ti(OEt) ₃ (O.C ₂ H ₄ .NH ₂) ₂ white solid (1.34g.)	19.84	19.70	5.33	5.76	0.24g.	0.25g.	125°/0.08 mm
	(HO.C ₂ H ₄ .NH ₂) ₂ (0.41g.)								
2.	Ti(OPr) ₄ (3.66g.)	Ti(OPr) ₃ (O.C ₂ H ₄ .NH ₂) ₂ white solid (3.44g.)	10.46	10.60	4.37	4.91	0.76	0.77	120°/0.5 mm
	(HO.C ₂ H ₄ .NH ₂) (0.70g.)								
3.	Ti(OBu ⁿ) ₄ (3.74g.)	Ti(OBu ⁿ) ₃ (O.C ₂ H ₄ .NH ₂) ₂ colorless viscous liquid (3.6g.)	14.57	14.63	4.08	4.28	..	..	..
	(HO.C ₂ H ₄ .NH ₂) (0.64g.)								
4.	Ti(OEt) ₄ (1.68g.)	Ti(OEt) ₂ (O.C ₂ H ₄ .NH ₂) ₂ white solid	18.61	18.56	10.67	10.85	0.85	0.87	Sublimes at 80° and distills at 120°/ 0.01 mm.
	(HO.C ₂ H ₄ .NH ₂) (0.86g.)								
5.	Ti(OPr) ₄ (1.95g.)	Ti(OPr) ₂ (O.C ₂ H ₄ .NH ₂) ₂ white solid (1.00g.)	16.72	16.73	10.05	9.72	0.81	0.82	..
	(HO.C ₂ H ₄ .NH ₂) (0.86g.)								
6.	Ti(OBu ⁿ) ₄ (3.71g.)	Ti(OBu ⁿ) ₂ (O.C ₂ H ₄ .NH ₂) ₂ white semisolid	15.36	15.24	8.80	8.91	..	..	..
	(HO.C ₂ H ₄ .NH ₂) (1.36g.)								

TABLE II

Sl. No.	Reactants.	Product, state, and yield.	% Titanium.		% Nitrogen.		Alcohol in azetropo.	
			Found.	Reql.	Found.	Reql.	Found.	Reql.
1.	$\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_4$ + $(\text{HO.C}_2\text{H}_4.\text{NH}_2)$ (1.70g.)	$\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})(\text{O.C}_2\text{H}_4.\text{NH}_2)_3$ white solid (2.73g.)	17.66	17.54	15.33	15.38	1.28g.	1.26g.
2.	$\text{Ti}(\text{OPr})_4$ + $(\text{HO.C}_2\text{H}_4.\text{NH}_2)$ (1.05g.)	$\text{Ti}(\text{OPr})(\text{O.C}_2\text{H}_4.\text{NH}_2)_3$ white solid (2.82g.)	16.92	16.68	14.56	14.63	...	..
3.	$\text{Ti}(\text{OBu}^n)_4$ + $(\text{HO.C}_2\text{H}_4.\text{NH}_2)$ (1.45g.)	$\text{Ti}(\text{OBu}^n)(\text{O.C}_2\text{H}_4.\text{NH}_2)_3$ white solid	16.01	15.90	13.46	13.55	..	..
4.	$\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_4$ + $(\text{HO.C}_2\text{H}_4.\text{NH}_2)$ (2.50g.)	$\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4.\text{NH}_2)_4$ white solid (2.73g.)	16.03	16.63	10.35	19.45	1.62	1.88
5.	$\text{Ti}(\text{OPr})_4$ + $(\text{HO.C}_2\text{H}_4.\text{NH}_2)$ (1.47g.)	$\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4.\text{NH}_2)_4$ white solid (1.68g.)	16.40	16.63	19.35	19.45	1.49	1.43
6.	$\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_4$ + $(\text{HO.C}_2\text{H}_4.\text{NH}_2)$ (3.25g.)	$\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4.\text{NH}_2)_4.\text{HO.C}_2\text{H}_4.\text{NH}_2$ light yellow crystalline semi-solid (2.3g.)	13.75	13.72	19.80	20.05	1.75	1.76
7.	$\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_4$ + $(\text{HO.C}_2\text{H}_4.\text{NH}_2)$ (2.50g.)	$\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4.\text{NH}_2)_4.\text{HO.C}_2\text{H}_4.\text{NH}_2$ solid (2.3g.)	13.75	13.72	19.50	20.05	..	..

another flask. The viscous mass on cooling crystallised as a crystalline pale yellow semisolid. It was dried under reduced pressure at $110^{\circ}/0.5$ mm (Table II; No. 7).

(b) To titanium alkoxide in benzene was added an excess of 2-hydroxyethylamine. Heat was produced on shaking and the amine settled down. The mixture was refluxed and the azeotrope was taken. On removing the bath and cooling, a viscous liquid, slightly pink in colour, was obtained. The supernatant liquid was decanted and the liquid was dried under reduced pressure. At $110^{\circ}/0.5$ mm the excess of the amine was removed (bath temperature 160°). A crystalline, pale yellow, low-melting solid was obtained (Table II; No. 6).

A portion of the above compound (1.05 g.) was heated under reduced pressure. At 160° bath temperature a colorless liquid distilled at $89-90^{\circ}/3$ mm, which was mainly the amine. A dirty white solid remained in the flask (0.86 g.). [Found: Ti, 16.63. Calc. for $Ti(O.C_2H_4.NH_2)_4$: Ti, 16.68%].

Molecular Weights of the Compounds

The molecular weights of the compounds were determined in benzene ebullioscopically (Table III).

TABLE III

Compound.	Obs.	Average.	Calc.
$Ti(OEt)_3(O.C_2H_4.NH_2)$	497.3, 485.4, 493.1, 501.3	494.2	243.0
$Ti(OPr^i)_3(O.C_2H_4.NH_2)$	655.8, 624.8, 621.3, 625.8	631.8	385.0
$Ti(OEt)_2(O.C_2H_4.NH_2)_2$	513.1, 522.0, 548.6, 522.6	528.5	258.0
$Ti(OPr^i)_2(O.C_2H_4.NH_2)_2$	610.3, 619.7, 620.3, 605.5	613.9	286.0

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